

Teacher perceptions of critical thinking skills within primary school design and technology

Abstract

Critical thinking skills and creativity have been lauded by many as key attributes sought from prospective employees for the future workplace in an ever changing world. Furthermore, a review of existing literature suggested the prevalence of critical thinking skills within design and technology (D&T) tasks. This study aimed to garner the perceptions of primary school teachers and establish, from a practitioner's viewpoint, whether critical thinking skills were evident within their classrooms during D&T sessions. The interviews followed a phenomenological approach and identified commonalities and differences between the teachers' viewpoints as they described the phenomena they had experienced. The eight interviewees were from different schools in different areas of the UK and ranged from experienced teachers to early career teachers. Teachers were asked about their experiences of teaching D&T before completing a hierarchical ordering exercise of skills they perceived were gained from D&T activities in primary schools. The data produced experiences, thoughts and opinions about teaching design and technology in primary schools and teacher perceptions of the role of critical thinking within them. Analysis of the interview transcripts identified critical thinking throughout the responses and categorised three main themes around the teaching of design and technology in primary schools: approaches, attitudes and outcomes. This study suggests that, in order for primary teachers to develop their pupils' critical thinking skills within design and technology, and thus develop technological literacy, there are issues that need addressing at both leadership and classroom levels such as training, resourcing and leadership priorities. Nevertheless, teachers interviewed in this small scale study confidently believe primary school pupils benefit from promoting critical thinking within D&T activities.

Key Words: Design and Technology, Critical Thinking, Teacher Perceptions, Primary/Elementary Education

INTRODUCTION

Defining critical thinking

Critical thinking is an often-lauded term used to describe a problem solving or independent thinking. In a report for the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), critical thinking is defined as “mainly inquisitive, a detective way of thinking” and creative thinking as “imaginative, the artist way of thinking” (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019, p.27). The analogy of a critical thinking detective and a creative thinking artist is potentially useful to distinguish the two but with the multitude of research in both disciplines, critical thinking is hard to distinguish with one clear definition (Ab Kadir 2018; Wei 2020; Yang 2009).

Willingham (2020) suggests that critical thinking is a combination of novel thinking, self-directed thinking and effective thinking and Chew et al. (2020) as “seeing both sides of the issue, reasoning, deducing and inferring conclusions” (p.1). Lai (2011) encourages the view that defining critical thinking depends upon whether it is during the process, the end product or as a stand-alone higher order thinking skill. Barnett (1997) also has the view that defining the concept of critical thinking is dependent upon how it is used and identifies four different ways of utilising the skill: as a stand-alone discipline, as knowledge used practically, engaged politically and as strategic thinking. The most widely viewed definition is the work of Richard Ennis who suggests that critical thinking is “reflective thinking focused on deciding what to believe or do” (Ennis, 2018, p.166)

The Cambridge University Press (CUP) released a series titled Life Competencies Framework (2019), with the aim to prepare students for the changing world ahead. Although originally designed for English language development, critical thinking is sub-divided into three categories: critical evaluation, analytical framework and synthesising ideas. Whilst the OECD detective is a simple analogy and Ennis’s definition is widely used, this study used the CUP model as a simple way to define critical thinking to participants during the interview. The development of critical thinking within the subject area of design and technology, and in particular within primary schools is an area this paper focuses upon particularly.

Critical thinking and Design and Technology

There are many researchers that link this metacognitive skill as being synonymous with the subject of design and technology. Rauscher and Badenhorst (2021 p.1) state that teachers are more likely to “encourage critical thinking in design and technology”. Nicholl (2017) suggests that within D&T activities pupils need to be empathetic to their client’s needs and that empathy is “embodied within an overall disposition to think critically.” (p.156). Additionally, Wei (2020) identified critical thinking processes during an analysis of design journals of junior high school students.

Spuzic et al. (2016) determines that within engineering, criticality and creativity are valuable skills. Whilst creative thinking can be seen as imaginative and critical thinking more analytical, both have worth in design and engineering. The report cites Adriansen’s (2010) table that attempts to differentiate the two cognitive skills. Mulnix (2012) concurs with the above and that there should be a clear distinction between creative thinking and critical thinking as they are not “equivalent”.

Table 1:1 Idealised differences between criticality and creativity

Creativity	Criticality
Imaginative	Rational
Non-judgemental	Evaluative
Generative	Selective
Holistic	Analytical
Constructing	Deconstructing
Transcending the framework	Within the framework
Open to serendipity	Work systematically
Iterative process with detours	Linear process

Taken from Table 1 Spuzic et al (2016, p.5)

When to teach critical thinking

Both Facione (1990, 2000) and Rauscher and Badenhorst (2020) build upon the practicalities of teaching critical skills to children and young people and the ‘dispositions’ to developing this higher order thinking skills. Facione (2000) promotes ‘habits of mind’ and that this type of thinking is valuable not just for older students but can be taught to younger children at primary level. Chew et al. (2020) agree that critical thinking “should be encouraged and instilled in students starting from a young age” (2020, p.249) and Gelerstein et al. (2016) suggest primary schools as the most advantageous time to teach critical thinking (p.40). Willingham concurs, and additionally suggests that “children are more capable than we thought” (2020, p.45).

With the above in mind, three key research questions evolved for the wider study and the main emphasis of this article ‘*What are teacher perceptions and understanding of critical thinking in primary schools within design and technology sessions?*’.

METHODOLOGY

To understand the views of participants, one must interpret what has been expressed and therefore an interpretivist, epistemological stance was chosen consistent with a qualitative approach. This study aimed for an ethnographical feel, exploring the participants experiences and seeking to understand perceptions and thus a phenomenological approach was taken.

Phenomenological Approach

Phenomenology is a description of a participants experiences without bias and can be seen as a philosophical exercise (Silverman, 2013, p.99) and a precursor to future research investigations. During the wider study, aspects of the phenomenological approach were taken rather than a holistic and purist commitment. Minimising interviewer bias, open ended questions and seeking opinions was evident throughout but there was also a structure throughout the interview focusing towards critical thinking. The results of this paper relate solely to the discussion around critical thinking within the interview.

Participants

This study had eight participants gathered from social media, contacts within schools and as can be seen from (Table 1:2), the majority of those who completed the interview were very experienced. I will declare here that I did know some of the interviewees but had worked with them previously.

Table 1:2: Overview of participant expertise

Which of these best describes you	Are you the D&T coordinator (or equ)
Participants who expressed interest and completed the interview	
10 years+ experience	No
6 years + experience	No
6 years + experience	Yes
2 years+ experience	No
Early Careers Teacher	No

Whilst having a breadth of experience was positive, having participants from around the country (Figure 1.1) provided an even wider experience.

Figure 1.1: Participants' locations

This could be seen as both a positive and a negative. The benefits were getting a wide range of opinions from a large cross section of the country where training and expertise might be different but conversely it might be more challenging to explain why certain beliefs and perceptions have been expressed. With a phenomenological approach however, the emphasis is upon exploring and identifying themes and raising further questions rather than reasoning why something happens.

Ethical Considerations

The study followed guidelines set out by the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018) and an ethics form was approved by the Faculty of Education at University of Cambridge which assured the safety of the participants through core principles of anonymity, informed consent and the freedom to withdraw were at the forefront of any decisions throughout the process.

Hierarchical activity

INTRODUCE JAMBOARD

As part of the interview process, participants accessed a ‘Jamboard’, an online interactive whiteboard, and were asked to move ‘sticky notes’ into a hierarchal order. Each note represented a different pupil attribute during D&T activities taken from the Hendley and Lyle (1996) study who asked pupils about their learning.

Figure 1.2: Jamboard example

The below table shows the outcomes and places values upon the hierarchy. Learning items placed as most commonly seen by teachers receive 5 points, second most commonly seen learning receive 4 and so on. *Working resiliently* and *problem solving* were clearly elements of learning teachers considered as beneficial from high quality D&T activities. Interestingly, *well finished products* and *excellent drawings* were not mentioned at all. Throughout the discussions over this activity, teachers talked about the design process being important, more so than the end product. *Critical thinking* was specifically mentioned by three out of eight interviewees (see Mode column representing how often each area of learning was chosen) but usually lower down in the hierarchy. The question to ask could be whether skills mentioned previously, problem solving for example, is in fact a key part of critical thinking itself.

Table 1:4: Jamboard analysis; in order of frequency

Areas of Learning (from Hendley and Lyle (1993))	Ada	Alex	Caroline	Elizabeth	Joe	Mary	Pat	Rosalind	Total	Mode
Working resiliently	3			5	3	4	5	3	23	6
Problem solving	1	1	1	3	1	2	4	4	17	8
Imaginative and creative thinking	2		5	4	4				15	4
Asking questions		2	4		2		2		10	4
Listening to the ideas of others	4	3				3			10	3
Working well with others	5					5			10	2
Making and testing predictions			2				3	2	7	3
Thinking critically						1	1	5	7	3
Explanations of why something happened				1	5				6	2
Finding information		5							5	1
Planning and designing carefully		4							4	1
Suggesting ways to improve				2				1	3	2
Following instructions			3						3	1
Clear and relevant ideas									0	0
Excellent drawings produced									0	0
Well finished products									0	0

Thematic analysis

I then returned to the transcripts with this structure and the number of ‘units of meaning’ associated with each of the above themes was recorded and quantified. This was transferred into a spreadsheet and the results set out below. The blue coloured boxes denote the most mentioned theme within each interview, orange boxes the least frequency. As can be seen, critical thinking was the most commonly discussed theme but it must also be stated that there was a question specifically about this within the interview.

Table 1.5 Overview of themes from NVivo; in order of frequency

Thematic analysis	Emerging theme	Ada	Alex	Caroline	Elizabeth	Joe	Mary	Pat	Rosalind	Total
Outcomes	Critical thinking	11	8	10	5	7	11	8	4	64
Approaches	Creative and cross curricular	11	6	8	8	4	5	9	8	59
Attitudes	Teacher attitudes	3	10	7	6	4	10	3	8	51
Attitudes	Leadership and priorities	6	9	10	2	6	4	6	6	49
Approaches	Resource driven approaches	6	4	6	6	2	2	6	9	41
Outcomes	Resilience and problem solving	7	2	7	3	4	2	7	8	40
Attitudes	Pupil enthusiasm	4	3	3	6	4	6	3	10	39
Approaches	Collaboration	5	4	4	3	4	10	2	5	37
Outcomes	Inclusive	8	2	4	3	7	7	3	2	36

Interview analysis

One criticism of phenomenography is the challenge for the researcher to eliminate their preconceived ideas and focus on themes and patterns analysed from the transcripts (Webb, 1997). In addition, “different people may experience the same ‘thing’ in different ways.” (Bell, 2016) and a researcher would need to be aware of the

differing opinions upon the same subjects. However, by continually being aware of researcher bias the analysis retained an interpretive stance and became demonstrative of a “reflexive, reactive interaction between the researcher and the decontextualised data that are already interpretations of a social encounter” Cohen et al. (2011). Throughout the process, I maintained as much of a phenomenological stance as possible and mindful of maintaining consistency with this choice of research method.

Through analysing the transcripts, there were examples of critical thinking throughout the interviews albeit not always explicitly. Defining critical thinking skills was initially an area some respondents asked for clarification. I used the aforementioned Cambridge University Press (CUP) definition of critical thinking, from their series of Life Competencies Framework (2019), to stimulate discussion where necessary and teachers were able to openly talk about their experiences. The three key areas of ‘critical evaluation’, ‘analytical framework’ and ‘synthesising ideas’ became themes arising from within the interviews and teachers reflected upon occasions that they had examples of critical thinking within the classroom without realising.

During a discussion about D&T projects teachers had taught, elements of all three categories of critical thinking were apparent. Examples of critical evaluation provided by the interviewees included making predictions about the products they were making and the consequences of potential design choices. Whether this be through the design process which many teachers were able to clearly communicate, or through trial and error, the teachers were able to identify children who had the “skills to be able to explain what they were doing, and what would what they thought would work better.” (Ada).

Analytical framework examples included a range of problem-solving techniques. From children identifying problems and then reasoning as to how to approach the issue, to how children described and justified choices made within their given project. To be able to differentiate between critical and thinking and problem solving, Caroline suggested that “problem solving, to me is kind of the basis form of critical thinking, you've got problem solving where you solve a problem. And that can be a very small problem or a bigger one. And whereas critical thinking is more, you're kind of anticipating problems as they come up. And you're, you're kind of preparing for that and thinking, ‘Well, okay, if I do that, then that might happen. So how can I stop that’ and things like that”.

The final sub theme from the CUP (2019) of synthesising ideas can be defined as solving problems collaboratively or using ideas and information from different sources to create a structured plan. Ada described this as an “understanding is how to get from A to B, and use all these bits and pieces in between.”

The relevance of critical thinking within D&T tasks as a development of pupil outcomes is one that was mentioned favourably by the interviewees. Whilst Rosalind’s view was “I don't think much about thinking critically...well, just that I haven't thought about it myself much”, Alex was more forthright in the opinion that “D&T activities lend themselves perfectly to critical thinking” because, “D&T tasks lend themselves more than other tasks to being critically analysed”.

When discussing which children Ada felt demonstrated critical thinking skills, she gave the example where children look at their designs and “think critically about it and what they could improve, I guess, yeah, there's some children that it comes automatically.” Mary agrees with this whilst surmising that children “must think more critically than I had ever sort of given them credit for”. However, interviewees recognised the fact that not all children will naturally have this instinct, or perhaps even have had the prior experience, and this is key to planning future teaching opportunities.

Pat provides an example of a teaching technique to develop critical thinking skills within an Early Years environment: “it's also something that we sometimes teach explicitly, not criticizing each other's work

necessarily, but perhaps we'll look at maybe a piece of art or something, and we'll talk about what we like about it". Modelling skills to enable them to develop critical thinking skills is something that Ada also suggests as important and that she would "deliberately make a mistake and model those critical thinking skills so that would be beneficial to them."

DISCUSSION

Critical thinking was evident throughout the interviews and many examples of pupil using critical thinking skills were stated by the interviewees. Whilst it could be said that the interview structure or researcher bias aided this, during the analysis of attitudes towards D&T activities examples of critical thinking emerged throughout, consciously or subconsciously, even before the subject of critical thinking arose. One could suggest the importance of critical thinking within D&T activities is supported not only with the interviewee findings but also the research by Nicholl (2017), Spuzic et al. (2016) and Wei (2020).

Whilst nine themes emerged from the wider study analysis, elements of critical thinking were evident within many of them. Initially, some teachers needed further explanation of what critical thinking actually meant within a D&T context. Ab Kadir (2018) suggests that teacher subject knowledge of critical thinking is an issue if it is to be promoted within classrooms. All respondents in this study however gave examples of critical thinking before critical thinking was first mentioned. This led me to conclude that critical thinking skills do exist within D&T activities if the accuracy of these eight interviews could be verified.

By specifically questioning about critical thinking within the interview, it was expected to have an impact upon the responses and some could say it could be disregarded as a null and void if a true phenomenological stance was followed. Whilst maintaining a phenomenological stance as much as possible, I needed to be pragmatic about the how much could be achieved phenomenologically. Identifying areas of critical thinking skills throughout the interviews was evident of the impact it had within D&T activities but again it must be stated that this is just a small-scale study and making sweeping statements is challenging without further evidence.

To fully understand the role of critical thinking with primary D&T it could require a different research methodology. For instance, gathering evidence in practice to support the theories suggested from the respondents within this study would aid the triangulation of evidence for the notion that critical thinking is a valuable part of D&T activities. From this small-scale project, teachers provide evidence of critical thinking apparent in D&T activities. However, it could be of value to further investigate this and to evidence it in action, perhaps through a series of observations and lesson studies. These potential research avenues only transpired after consideration of this study, deep analysis through a phenomenological research stance. The aim of phenomenology is to gather themes and create further questions. To that extent, I have created more questions than answers and whilst I cannot say that this study has been purely phenomenological, I have endeavoured to use this approach to understand teacher perceptions of critical thinking in D&T activities in a very small scale.

From a personal point of view, this research has enabled me to reflect upon my own practice and consider how to utilise my understanding of teacher perceptions within the training I deliver for trainee teachers at the University of Cambridge and also within my school D&T activities. The critical thinking skills and using D&T as a conduit to provide children with skills for their future materialised as important values from these interviews. The positivity from teacher within these interviews about the subject was also very pleasing and to complete further research to evidence the existence, and importance, of critical thinking within primary school D&T activities is one that I personally feel has value in order for us to deliver high quality activities so that pupils have the skills to make "an essential contribution to the creativity, culture, wealth and well-being of the nation" (DfE 2013).

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